

THE SAFE SCHOOL INITIATIVE: ENHANCING CHILD PROTECTION POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN A RURAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the implementation of the Child Protection Policy (CPP) in Philippine schools, specifically focusing on a rural elementary school. The researchers used the action research method, interviewing and conducting focus group discussions with the school head, six teachers, and one representative each from the Supreme Elementary Learner Government, School Parent-Teacher Association, and Barangay Local Government Unit. The gathered data were analyzed using the thematic analysis approach. This study reveals varying levels of CPP awareness and implementation in the school, the extent of responsiveness and support of the school in the CPP implementation, and diverse challenges encountered by the teachers in imposing discipline in the classroom. To help improve its implementation, the researchers developed, implemented, and evaluated the “Support and Advocacy for a Friendly Environment (SAFE) School Initiative,” a school-community-driven intervention aimed at enhancing awareness and responsiveness to the CPP. Hence, this initiative has significantly contributed to the enhancement and improvement of the school stakeholders’ awareness and responsiveness to the CPP implementation. Therefore, the researchers recommend that the school sustain and enhance the SAFE School Initiative to realize the full potential of the CPP. Additionally, a larger sample may be utilized, considering its areas of limitations.

Keywords: *Action Research, Child Protection Policy, SAFE School Initiative*

INTRODUCTION

Protecting children means protecting the future. Children play a vital role in the development and progress of the nation. Hence, government agencies, both internationally and locally, implement laws and policies that advocate child protection. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) is a legally binding international agreement setting out the civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights of every child regardless of their race, religion, or abilities (UNICEF UK, 2024, June 26). In Georgia, the key priorities of the European Union and Georgia for 2021-2027 were the implementation of the Code on the Rights of the Child by harmonizing all relevant laws and strengthening national mechanisms to protect children against all forms of violence (UNICEF, 2024). In Indonesia, an institution has been established to address bullying through supervision, namely the independent supervisory institution, the Indonesian Child Protection Commission, which serves as the government's response to the significant increase in cases of criminal acts of bullying, especially against children (Andryawan & Wulansari, 2024). In Malaysia, a child is recognized an asset of the society and a key for prosperity and development, thus, safeguarding the welfare of every child is acknowledged through an act titled "Child Act 2001". This Act covers children that in need of care, protection, and rehabilitation, children "beyond control", which refers to children who are difficult to manage by their parents or guardians, and children in conflict with the law (Razali & Nawang, 2022). These laws and protocols demand child protection in every part of the country. Hence, intensive awareness and proper implementation of these mandates should be maintained or strengthened.

In the Philippines, there is a law that protects women and children against physical, psychological, sexual and economic abuse called the Republic Act 7610, otherwise known as the Special Protection of Children Against Child Abuse, Exploitation, and Discrimination Act that provides a legal basis to protect children from all forms of abuse, neglect, cruelty, exploitation, and discrimination, and other conditions prejudicial to their development (Republic of the Philippines, 1992.). The Republic Act 9262 or the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004 that aims to protect women and children from abuse and violence and ensures to provide support services and assistance (Republic of the Philippines, 2004). Additionally, there is a government agency called Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) mandated to implement social protection and provide protective services (Republic of the Philippines, 1992). Likewise, the Department of Education (DepEd) provides and secures children to learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment (DepEd, 2013). According to Shekhar & Rai (2025), safeguarding children is a foundation not an option to a just, peaceful, and inclusive society. These laws and orders signify individual accountability in safeguarding children. Thus, effective implementation and coordination of these mandates is required to achieve the common goal which is to uphold children's welfare and secure children's future.

Child protection is fundamental in the environment where children can be exposed to abuse and violence. Hence, schools which are the children's learning environment and a place where teachers, administrators, parents, and children collaborate with each other

for learning should maintain safety and implement protocols in protecting children as well as other school stakeholders. Consequently, DepEd issued the DepEd Order 40, s. 2012, entitled DepEd Child Protection Policy, to secure and protect the children from abuse, violence, exploitation, discrimination, bullying, and other forms of abuse (DepEd, 2012) in school settings. According to Estremera (2018), the policy aims to protect children under the tutelage of teachers and school administrators, and thus, it is imperative to implement and disseminate it accordingly in the best interest of all concerned. The policy emphasizes the use of positive and non-violent disciplinary approaches in place of corporal punishment (DepEd, 2012). However, due to the mandate of the policy, teachers nowadays have trouble handling students' misbehavior and impose discipline on them. According to Casipe and Bete (2023), the Child Protection Policy (CPP) causes hesitation among teachers in imposing disciplinary actions, as they are often restricted from implementing appropriate measures and may even face accusations of child abuse. The teachers face criminalization because of the perception that when a student experiences violence, it is considered negligence of the teacher, because the school should be a place to protect students (Yenny et al., 2020). Furthermore, sentiments shared by teachers on social media highlight concerns such as the decline of values among the younger generation, the perception that enforcing discipline is now treated as a crime due to the CPP, and the observation that even some parents today struggle to discipline their children. Additionally, former DepEd official advised teachers to pause from teaching whenever they get angry due to the news about the public school teacher who went viral on social media after berating her students live on TikTok (GMA Integrated News, 2024). Relatively, incorporating the CPP in the classroom is very challenging for teachers, especially if the learners behave disrespectfully and impolitely. Moreover, these circumstances cause damage to the image of the teachers as the second parent of the learners and the school as their second home (Bayuca, 2020). This has become a challenge for teachers in managing student misbehavior, as it impacts overall classroom management. Discipline plays a crucial role in classroom management, though it is often mistakenly equated with punishment. The rights and privileges of teachers are also invalidated, and they are sometimes falsely accused. Hence, the CPP is being misused against teachers.

On the other hand, several studies reveal that the school's awareness influences the effectiveness of the implementation of CPP. According to Matulac and Zamora (2020), the top-level management and teachers are the vanguards of the school, and they have a better understanding of child protection in terms of managing and handling the children's and guardians' concerns. However, in the study of Bayuca (2020), schools were found to be aware of the policy but lacked strict implementation. Similarly, there is an establishment of a Child Protection Committee (CPC) in schools, but it needs further awareness of the framework of CPP (Estremera, 2018). "Ignorance of the law is no excuse"; therefore, awareness and responsiveness of all school stakeholders—school leaders, teachers, pupils, and community—to the CPP is a must.

Relatively, based on the School Improvement Plan (SIP) for the school year 2016-2019 of the school, attached to this is the accomplished school-based Child Protection/Anti-Bullying Policy Implementation Checklist (Annex 2B of DepEd Order No.

44, s. 2015) report for the school year 2016-2017 wherein the school obtained an overall score of 6 out of 20 items. This shows that only 30% of the items were compliant with the school in the implementation of DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012 and DepEd Order No. 55, s. 2013 including the school-based referral and monitoring system to address child abuse and bullying cases, an adopted conflict resolution mechanism that respects the rights of indigenous people, mapped out available resources in the community for possible linkages or networking for cases needing referrals, active coordination with government and Non-Government Organizations (NGO), a clear policy on the use of positive and non-violent discipline for children, and a strong student participation in the promotion of child protection and anti-bullying policies of the school. On the other hand, the 70% that was not in place in the school were the written school-based child protection and/or anti-bullying policies, code of conduct for the stakeholder and its specific provisions, promotion or information dissemination, written procedures in conducting disciplinary proceedings in cases of offenses committed by pupils, students, or learners, an established system for identifying students who may be suffering from significant harm based on physical, emotional, or behavioral signs, existing records of all proceedings related to bullying and child abuse cases using the Intake Sheet (Annex B of DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012 or Appendix B of DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2015), separate records related to complex cases of bullying and child abuse using Intake Sheet (Annex A of DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012 or Appendix B of DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2015), submission of consolidated reports of bullying and child abuse cases to the Division Office, the establishment of Child Protection Committee (CPC), annual capacity building activities for the members of the CPC, regular meetings to discuss appropriate interventions, initiated information dissemination, programs and organized activities for the protection of children from abuse, exploitation, violence, harm, and bullying, and a feedback mechanism to monitor its implementation. Hence, the researchers of this study seek to validate these issues and concerns of the school for the implementation of the CPP and develop and implement an intervention thereafter.

Enhancement of the CPP implementation in the school is evident through different proposed interventions. In the study of Asio et al. (2020), a seminar that aims to revisit the Child Protection Policy for the awareness of school stakeholders is recommended. Training modules that include positive and non-violent discipline in classroom management, anger and stress management, and gender sensitivity should be included in seminars to be conducted. This recommendation is supported by the study of Bayuca (2020) and Baronia (2020), that highlights regular monitoring and observation of the CPP implementation. Likewise, capacity building, community engagement, training and program implementation are crucial towards effective implementation of the policy (Andaya et al., 2025; Andaya & Patricio, 2025; Manacho, 2024; Atilano-Tang, 2023) that should be provided by the school leaders to the school personnel to educate them about the CPP and its practices (Antiza & Labitad, 2024). Additionally, to enhance awareness and execution of CPP in elementary schools specifically, the action plan is the proposed intervention in the study of Estremera (2018). According to Casipe and Bete (2023), a lack of awareness in the CPP can lead to confusion and misunderstanding of their roles and responsibilities as direct implementers, and as a result, teachers may face challenges in dealing with students' diverse behavior. Therefore, a deep understanding of the CPP

is critical to the success of the policy's implementation. Moreover, the provision of legal assistance and the establishment of support mechanisms for teachers and other school personnel are directed to help teachers and implementers be protected while performing their roles and responsibilities. Consequently, the different interventions stated offer a variety of recommendations that are relevant for the improvement and enhancement of the implementation of the CPP.

In the school's context, a proposed intervention to help improve and enhance the CPP implementation is through the "SAFE" School Initiative. SAFE stands for Support and Advocacy for a Friendly Environment. This is a school-community-driven initiative that aims to improve and enhance the implementation of CPP, specifically in a rural elementary school. It comprises three categories: (a) an orientation workshop that aims to revisit the CPP, enhance the awareness of its components, and the execution of the CPP in school, (b) establishment of a Child Protection Committee to strengthen the CPP implementation, and (c) provision of a school handbook as a reference of the SAFE School Initiative. Moreover, this aimed to capacitate teachers in exercising their roles and responsibilities as classroom managers and to foster awareness of the school and community as the policy implementers, specifically the parents and the school children.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to develop and implement an intervention to improve the implementation of the Child Protection Policy (CPP) in a rural elementary school. Specifically, this research aimed to:

1. Identify the issues and concerns in the implementation of CPP,
2. Describe the developed and organized Support and Advocacy for a Friendly Environment (SAFE) School Initiative, and
3. Explain the evaluation results on the acceptability of the SAFE School Initiative.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers employed a qualitative approach incorporating an action research method to determine the issues and concerns in the implementation of the CPP. Action research is an approach to educational research that is used to examine and improve pedagogy and practice, and a process to gather evidence to implement change in practices (Clark et al., 2020). Thus, this method fits in with the study, as it aims to develop and implement the proposed intervention in the enhancement of the CPP of the school.

Specifically, the researchers adapted the action research cycle framework (Stringer, 2007; Digo & Labor, 2022), which describes addressing practical challenges in the work fields and promotes collaboration and reflection in providing solutions for this study. This action research approach is recursive, recycling stages of investigation and

inquiry toward detailed procedures and specific solutions (Lufungulo et al., 2021). The stages comprise (1) looking: a gathering of data to describe the situation; (2) thinking: exploring, analyzing, interpreting, and explaining; and (3) acting: planning, implementing, and evaluating suitable solutions. In the context of this study, the three stages are explained as follows: (1) Looking: An interview was conducted with the school stakeholders to describe the implementation of the CPP; (2) Thinking: Based on the data gathered, the researchers utilized a focus group discussion with the school stakeholders to develop and organize the SAFE School Initiative to address the issues and concerns of the rural elementary school in the implementation of the CPP by presenting the proposed components of the initiative of the researchers in collaboration with the suggestions and recommendations of the school stakeholders; and (3) Acting: This stage includes writing a proposal for the implementation of the SAFE School Initiative, specifically the orientation workshop, which is the major category of the initiative, and an interview to evaluate its acceptability. These three stages of the action research method were recycled through a reflection where enhancement and improvement were developed.

The Participants

There are ten school stakeholders, consisting of eight internal stakeholders who are directly involved in or affected by the daily educational operations of the school and two external stakeholders, or those who are not directly involved in or affected by the daily educational operations of the school but have a strong interest in collaborating with and/or supporting the school to address its concerns and improve its performance (DepEd, 2022), who took part in the interview and focus group discussions. The researchers employed purposeful sampling, as it provides a homogeneous sample that is of specific interest and relevant to the study (Andrade, 2020). The participants were selected based on the following criteria: for school personnel, they are school personnel of the rural elementary school with at least two years in service and have a direct interaction with educational leaders; for pupils, they are members of Supreme Elementary Learner Government (SELG) for at least two years; for parents, they are members of School Parent-Teacher Association (SPTA) for at least two years; and for community representatives, they have been members of the Barangay Council for the Protection of Children (BCPC) for at least two years. From this criteria, one school head, six teachers, one SELG representative, one SPTA representative, and one Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) representative in the respective school were selected. The participants' profiles were as follows: Gender (Male: 1 and Female: 9); institutional affiliation (DepEd: 8, community linkages: 2); position (principal: 1, proficient teacher: 6, pupil: 1, parent: 1, BCPC: 1); and educational attainment (bachelor's degree: 7, secondary school graduate: 2, elementary undergraduate: 1).

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized an interview guide to provide an in-depth response to the study. The interview guide questions were based on the Child Protection Policy Implementation Checklist from DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2015, otherwise known as

Guidelines on the Enhanced School Improvement Plan (SIP) Process and the School Report Card (SRC), to identify the issues and concerns in the implementation of CPP, and were also used for the focus group discussion to develop and organize the SAFE School Initiative. Additionally, to explain the evaluation results on the acceptability of the initiative, the researchers used an interview guide based on the implementation of the initiative.

Data Collection

Unstructured interviews, focus group discussions, audio recordings, and note-taking were conducted for ten participants after informed consent was obtained. The interview was designed to encourage participants to share their personal experiences and perspectives on the issues and concerns in the implementation of CPP. Likewise, the focus group discussion was utilized to develop and organize an intervention. Thereafter, an interview was conducted to explain the evaluation results on the acceptability of the initiative. The questions were open-ended and allowed participants to share their thoughts in their own words. The audio recording and note-taking were utilized to record detailed information and help ensure the accuracy and consistency of the given data.

Data Analysis

The data collected from unstructured interviews, focus group discussions, audio recordings, and note-taking were transcribed manually and analyzed using the six-stage thematic analysis approach of Braun and Clarke, consisting of familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, generating initial themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up (Byrne, 2021). According to Kiger and Varpio (2020), thematic analysis is a powerful analytical method for qualitative research that involves interpretation in the processes of selecting codes and constructing themes. Thus, this approach was useful in identifying themes and patterns in the participants' experiences and perspectives on the implementation of CPP in a rural elementary school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Issues and Concerns in the Implementation of CPP

This section reveals the issues and concerns in the implementation of CPP in a rural elementary school. Using the Thematic Analysis as a tool, the researchers managed to discuss its findings that were formulated in three themes: insufficient awareness of the school stakeholders on CPP implementation, limited school responsiveness and support for CPP implementation, and challenges in the classroom-level implementation of CPP.

Insufficient Awareness of the School Stakeholders on the Implementation of CPP

One of the identified themes as issues and concerns in the implementation of CPP is the awareness of the school stakeholders of its implementation. Most of the

participants noted that the school must ensure the security and safety of all the children; thus, the school must adhere to its implementation. Participant G stated, *“Kaipuhan talaga ina kay child-centered kita. Dapat talaga may child protection policy kita na inapairal nan inapatupad didi kay kapot naton an batit kay sinda mga fragile pa, vulnerable [That’s necessary because we are in a child-centered education. We need a child protection policy in place and implemented here because we are responsible of the children and they are still fragile and vulnerable] they need protection and that is policy.”* *“Dapat magkaigwa talaga sana para magkaigwa sin seguridad an mga batit na halimbawa may mga inaabuso, kaipuhan ta ina masuportahan,”* [It is necessary for the safety of the children, for instance if someone is being abused, they need to be supported], Participant I denoted. *“Importanteng-importante po ‘yon para sa akin kasi po mas magiging safe po ang mga bata, mas magiging gusto po nilang pumunta dito sa school kasi alam po nila na safe sila.”* [That’s very important to me because the children will be safer, and they will be more likely to come to school because they know they are safe], Participant H added. *“An pagkakaintindi ko talaga san child protection policy amo ‘yon na puproteksyonan mo an batit. Bawal talaga an corporal punishment.”* [My understanding of the child protection policy is that you must protect the child. Corporal punishment is really prohibited], according to Participant D.

On the other hand, some of the participants expressed their sentiments on its implementation, such as, *“Sa panahon niyan, an pagkakaigwa sin child protection policy bagan natutuon an pansin san gobyerno sa pagbantay para sa mga batit para sa seguridad...san wara pa CPP, an teacher pwede magpangaral sa mga batit.”* [Nowadays, the existence of a child protection policy seems to indicate that the focus of the government’s attention is on monitoring children for their safety...before the CPP, teachers could discipline children.] *“Dahil sa child protection policy masakit na magdisiplina sa mga bata. Hadlok na an maestra magdudot sa eskwela kay kun amo pa an makasuhan.”* [Because of the child protection policy, it’s difficult to discipline children. Teachers are now afraid to discipline children because they might get accused], expressed by Participant B. Another sentiment by Participant C, *“Magburarat ka lang sa batit, kakasuhan ka na. Diri pareho san panahon na maski uritan mo an mga batit, okay lang, niyan, may limit na sa inda an pag-urit, pagbaud, nan pagdisiplina.”* [Nowadays, even simply looking at a child can lead to complaint. Unlike before, when reprimanding children was acceptable, there are now limits on expressing anger, scolding, and disciplining them.] *“Mas mayad talaga na ibalik an corporal punishment.”* [It is better if corporal punishment were brought back], Participant F added. *“Problem na niyan an pagdiscipline sa batit kay pirme ka niyan i-DSWD, pwede ka kasuhan sin VAWC. So dahil habo mo makasuhan, gusto mo mag-awat sa service, makita ka lang sa mga batit but an learning dai magayon.”* [Discipline has become challenging nowadays because you might get reported to the DSWD, and you could be charged under VAWC. To avoid legal issues and to keep your position, teachers hesitate to intervene and simply observe the children, but the learning outcomes are no longer good], Participant G said.

Additionally, some of the participants stated their ignorance of implementing the policy. *“Actually, ‘di ko man aram an rules san CPP kay kulang pa kami sa kaaraman sana.”* [Actually, I don’t know the rules of the CPP because we still lack knowledge about

that], Participant F said. *“Dai kita knowledgeable sa implementation, wara pa ako orientation about diyan.”* [We are not knowledgeable about the implementation, I haven't had an orientation about that yet] Participant E stated. *“Diri naton aram kun nano an appropriate talaga na pagdisiplina na ihahatag mo para sa batit. Diri siya na-orient talaga, diri in-depth an pagkaaram naton kun nano talaga an child protection policy. Igwa sin presence of ignorance san protocol”* [We really don't know what the appropriate discipline we must give to the children because it wasn't really oriented, we don't have an in-depth understanding of what the child protection policy really is. There is a presence of ignorance regarding the protocol], Participant D added. According to Asio et al. (2020), the school only complies with such a policy if the teachers are aware of it. The schools may be aware of the policy but not rigid in its implementation (Bayuca, 2020), and there may be an establishment of CPC in schools, but there needs to be further awareness of the framework of the policy (Estremera, 2018). According to the study of Antiza and Labitad (2024), teachers express their concern on issues such as equal treatment, teacher morale, and responsiveness regarding the policy implementation; thus, Responsiveness Theory was proposed to enhance CPP awareness through regular training and seminars. Additionally, the CPP is imperative to be implemented and disseminated because this promotes protection of the children from the teachers and school administrators (Estremera, 2018). These findings denote that awareness of the framework, components, and implementation of the CPP is the demand to be addressed. Therefore, this must be included in the development and organization of the intervention.

Limited School Responsiveness and Support for CPP Implementation

This theme shows how responsive the school is and how effective its support mechanisms are in implementing the CPP. Relatively, some of the participants agreed that the school has a Child Protection Committee, but it is not functional and lacks orientation. *“Sa school igwa sin child protection committee kaso nga lang dai man nagpafunction.”* [In our school, there is a child protection committee, but it is not functional], according to Participant B. Similarly to what Participant F stated, *“An aram ko lang an committee, school year 2016 ko pa ito nabagatan. Basta lang kami binutang an pangaran didto, ‘di man kami na-orient sana.”* [The only thing I know is the committee that was back in the school year 2016. They just put our names there and we weren't even oriented]. However, other participants noted that the school has not yet established a Child Protection Committee. *“Although nag-iexist na an CPP, ‘di pa kita naka-organize committee on CPP”* [Although the CPP already exists, we haven't organized yet committee on CPP], expressed by Participant G. *“Committee, wara man an school”* [The school doesn't have a committee] and *“Wara pa man CPC”* [There's no CPC yet] were stated by Participant C and Participant E, respectively. Additionally, the school has no written school-based child protection and/or anti-bullying policies and written procedures to guide in conducting disciplinary proceedings in cases of offenses committed by pupils or learners. *“Wara pa man kita document pero reminders igwa kita, just giving reminders to the pupils about safeguarding against abuses sa PTA meeting. Nagreremind ako sin antibullying, mga restrictions, mga prohibitions.”* [We don't have a document yet, but we have reminders, just giving reminders to the pupils about safeguarding against abuses in the PTA meeting. I reminded them about anti-bullying, restrictions, and prohibitions]

stated by Participant G. *“Igwa ngani sin bullying, may mga cases but itong mga incidents, those were not reported to the Division Office, kumbaga sa school level lang an settlement, diri siya nirereport.”* [There are cases of bullying, but these incidents were not reported to the Division Office, they were settled at the school level] Participant G added. *“Tapos may parent pa na nireklamo an teacher kay may samad [an batit]. Wara kami incidental report, wara man san written report.”* [And then a parent complained about the teacher because their child got injured [wound]. We didn’t have an incidental report, nor did we have a written report], stated by Participant F. *“Wara sin written so bagan nababalgar kasi diri mo pa aram an proseso...dapat talaga igwa nin written policy an eskwelahan.”* [There’s no written policy so it’s a bit confusing because you don’t know the process yet...the school really needs to have a written policy], according to Participant D. Relatively, the support and training provided to the stakeholders regarding the CPP were inadequate. *“Kalimitan an na-orient saaton an about sa children’s rights pero an sa child protection policy diri pa, an pag-implement wara pa.”* [Mostly, we are oriented about children’s rights but not yet about the child protection policy and its implementation], Participant D expressed. *“Wara pa man mga training, an sa Gender and Development (GAD) pa man lang, wara pa man kita sin idea ng gayod sana na policy.”* [We haven’t had any training yet, only in Gender and Development (GAD), and we still don’t have an idea about the policy], Participant C denoted. *“Wara pa man talaga sin activity o program about child protection policy”* [There have not yet been any activity or program related to the child protection policy], Participant B added. Likewise, there is an absence of guidelines in community linkages or school-based referral networking for bullying or child abuse cases in the school; thus, there are no proper complaint proceedings. *“Sa niyan diri man naki-coordinate [sa barangay] kay wara man malala na kaso, nasosolve na niyo...diri na inpapaluwas. Mas magayon kay adi man lang kita sa sarong barangay kaipuhan talaga an coordination...na dapat aram san barangay, aram san eskwelahan kay kun nano man an maitatabang san barangay, kun nano man an maitatabang san eskwelahan sa barangay, nasa lebel kita nan magayunon an sitwasyon pagnakacoordinate,”* [Right now, the school do not coordinate with the barangay because there is no serious cases and these are already solved by the school...it is not reported anymore. Since we are only in one barangay, it is better because coordination is really needed...the barangay should be informed so as the school, to extend help whatever the barangay and the school need, the situation will be better when there is a coordination], stated Participant C. Additionally, according to Participant G, *“Wara man coordination sa barangay.”* [There is no coordination with the barangay]. *“...kay pareho sa akon ito na nangyari, may kaso na nagdirekta ka sa luwas, ito palang kay concern mo an estudyante, dapat palang within the school muna tapos nogcommunity ka na.”* [...a similar situation happened to me that there was a case which was reported directly outside the school, but since your concern is the student, it should have been addressed within the school first before going to the community], stated Participant D. *“An hinimo san teacher, inkaistorya niya an kapitan, kaya lang an nangyari sadto dapat diri siya mabalangibog, kami lang dapat, kaya lang diri kaya handelon an mga tawo kaya dinumog, nagkaararaman. An teacher linuwas niya sa munisipyo, nan didto nalang nagkaayos, ‘di na nag-agi sa barangay kay dinudumog na.”* [What the teacher did was to have a conversation with the barangay captain and it should have been a private conversation, but the crowd was unable to handle so the teacher reported the matter to the municipal

office, and it was settled there; it did not go through the barangay because it was already crowded], according to Participant C. *“Igwa lang ako naaraman pero diri nakareport sa barangay, ongoing sana an kaso pero lain ‘yon nakalaog sa barangay, parang dinerehta ninda ‘yon sa DSWD. Tapos an panduwa, nagreklamo sa barangay, wara sa eskwelahan, diri siya nag-agi sa eskwelahan.* [I became aware of one case, but it was not reported to the barangay and that case was ongoing, but it was not reported to the barangay yet it appears to have been submitted directly to the DSWD. Then the second case, the complaint was filed at the barangay instead of being processed through the school], Participant I narrated. *“Minsan ‘pag nagsabi an batit sa teacher parang an teacher sabihon lang yaaw-yaaw lang ito, minsan diri inpapansin san teacher, nan pag minsan parang an teacher mismo inbabalewala ninda an mga batit. May mga batit man na nagsasabi sa magurang kaya minsan baga may mga magurang na nagkakadto sa school kasi masumat an batit sin pan-o si teacher di man ako pinansin. Insabihan lang ako sin mag-ingkod lang ako.”* [Sometimes when a child tells something to the teacher, the teacher seems to ignore it, saying that it is just a joke. Sometimes the teacher does not even pay attention and simply instructs the child to sit down. Some children instead tell their concern to their parents, which is why parents go to the school because of the child’s concern], stated by Participant J. Consequently, according to these statements, the school has no functional CPC, no reports and records of all proceedings related to bullying and child abuse cases, no written school-based CPP, written procedures to guide in conducting disciplinary proceedings in cases of offenses, inadequate support and training regarding the CPP, and an absence of guidelines in community linkages or school-based referral networking for bullying or child abuse cases. Relatively, awareness of the policy is having an establishment of the child protection policy committee that helps ensure responsiveness of the school community to the child protection issues (Antiza & Labitad, 2024). Baronía (2020) also suggested improving the school stakeholder’s participation in accordance with the CPP implementation and school leaders must ensure a democratic school environment where the students can freely express their grievances. Therefore, the school needs further understanding and awareness of the policy to address this shortfall for its rigid implementation.

Challenges in the Classroom-Level Implementation of CPP

Teachers are the leaders and managers of their classrooms. They are entitled as the second parent of their learners. Thus, it is their responsibility to safeguard the welfare of their school children from all forms of violence. Relatively, discipline is very significant in classroom management, and this is one of the concerns of the rural elementary school teachers about what and how they effectively discipline their pupils in adherence to the CPP. Participant F stated, *“An mga batit niyan pagsinaway mo, kadali lang mawara, taod-taod amo na naman pero kung igwa ka san punishment nag-aayos-ayos man kaya mas mayad talaga na ibalik an corporal punishment. Kaya lang kun irog sana, parang ikaw an mapapasala”* [Children today, when you ask them to behave, they listen, yet after a while, they still repeat the behavior, but if there is punishment, they behave better, so it would really be better to bring back corporal punishment but the problem is, you would end up facing the consequences], Participant E also stated, *“Mas bet ko an corporal discipline kasi talagang nasunod an mga batit.”* [I prefer corporal discipline because the children

became obedient]. *“Dako-dako ini na challenge sa akon kay pareho sadto na indisciplina mo siya pero sa part san magurang, lain siya mayad na disiplina... tinagan ninda sin iba na interpretasyon... iba an sumat san batit, iba man an ginibo mo, kaya ini na CPP, bagan kadako sadi na issue para...sa pagdisiplina san mga batit.”* [This is a big challenge for me because, just like before, you just disciplined the child, but on the part of the parents, it is a different kind of discipline...they gave it a different interpretation... the child gives a different version of the story of what actually happens, so this CPP seems to be a big issue for...disciplining the children], expressed by Participant C. Similarly, Participant D stated, *“Masakit siya, as a teacher kasi kun makikita mo an mga attitude niyan san batit, iba. Diri na sinda nakukuwa sa tingin, sa sitsit. Kun nano ito na aram mo na pagdisiplina, amo ito an iniimplement mo. Halimbawa, okay lang magpispis kasi diri man malalastrohan nan basta diri man manganaan an batit.”* [It is difficult for me as a teacher because children nowadays can no longer be managed through simple acts of discipline such as non-verbal cues. You use the disciplinary methods you are familiar with, for example, it becomes acceptable to pinch lightly because it won't leave marks on the child, as long as the child doesn't get hurt too much]. Participant A added, *“Mapagal magsugo sa batit nan dai na mapagsabihan kun may hinimo na maraot. An pag-apin san magurang sa batit amo pa an nasugod sa school”* [It is hard to give orders to children and to discipline them especially when their parents are overly protective and defensive].

Relatively, bullying and even child abuse cases were evident in the school. *“Sa laog talaga sin classroom, diri mo talaga ina maiwasan na an mga batit nagkakarantayan. Syempre kita 'di ta pa man aram kun nano an pagprotect sinda, kumbaga in general kita mag-urit. Sala san saro, nadadamay an iba.”* [Bullying is inevitable inside the classroom, and it is very challenging for us to manage such kind of behavior and prevent bullying since we are not aware of how to protect them], stated Participant D. *“Usuhunon ina didi maski nano na grade. Daghanon sana naghihiran, nagbabaransagan, pagkatapos burung-ilan tapos masumat sa magurang”* [That is very common at any grade level. Many children get into conflicts and complain to their parents], Participant F conveyed. *“Insusurunggod an mga batit, an mga daragko na mga batit inyayaraawan an mga saragday na mga batit. Igwa pa didi sin mga batit na maaram na magkutong, magkuwa nin mga kwarta sa mga saragday na mga batit”* [Higher grade children bully the younger children by taunting and taking their money], explained by Participant C. Another statement from Participant B, *“Saro sa mga challenges na na-encounter ko as a classroom teacher an kaso nin bullying. May mga bully na batit na dai maburubag-o an ugali na nagkakawsa pirme nin ribok sa klase hanggang sa mag-arapin na an magurang.”* [One of the challenges I have encountered as a classroom teacher is the case of bullying and the difficulty of addressing it, particularly when parents are involved]. *“May case ako na nakaabot sa principal. May nagsumat sa akon saro sa estudyante ko na may nagpaluwas san private part. An ginibo san school, kinaistorya po namon an parent san mga kaintra duman sa nangyari. Parang nagkaigwa lang agreement sa school na wara na sadto magluwas na pangyayari.”* [A case was reported to me involving my pupil who exposed his private part and it was escalated to the principal, and the school's action was to meet with the pupil's parents and they came to an agreement to keep the issue confidential], stated by Participant E. *“...inpaparabully siya kay nakikita ngani na may diperensya sa pag-iisip hanggang sa magbutas kay 'di na*

nakaya an pagbully. Inkaistorya ko an batit pati an magurang, na mag-eskwela, wara man, habo na. An cause san pagpundo, bullying". [A child is being bullied because of perceived mental health issues leading to refusal to attend to school even after talking to his parents], stated by Participant G. "...inwalaan niya [estudyante] ako. Ang lamesa ko dati inbagsak niya so an ginibo ko, inirog ko siya 'di nagpundo siya." [...a child threw tantrums and flipped over my desk, and what I did was I copied what he did, and that made him stop], expressed by Participant E. "*Daghanon didi an mga batit na inpapatrabaho. 'Pag hinapot mo kun kay nano kay absent, nagbantay sa batit, nagkadto sa bulod.* [Many children here have responsibilities outside the school. Some take care of their young siblings, while others work in the fields, which causes them to be absent from school]. *May saro pa ako na estudyante na nagkuwa siya san picture san batit [kaklase], tapos amo an hinimo niya na profile tapos tuda an chat. Nagreklamo an magurang kaya an hinimo ko sadto kay nagkadi an magurang, pinatawag ko man an saro [magurang] para aram niya.*" [I have a pupil who used his classmate's picture to create a social media account and used it to chat with others so the parent complained about it that is why I talked to the parents to inform them about the issue], as narrated by Participant F. Relatively, according to Casipe and Bete (2023), CPP implementation causes accusations of child abuse to teachers; thus, it is difficult for them to impose discipline on their students. Likewise, the reason why teachers face criminalization is because of the perception that when a student experiences violence, it is considered negligence of the teacher because the school should be a place to protect students (Yenny et al., 2020). Consequently, the teachers have trouble in imposing discipline on their pupils because of invalidating the CPP, resulting in accusations. In connection with this, a lack of awareness in the policy can lead to confusion and misunderstanding of their roles and responsibilities as a direct implementer; hence, teachers may face challenges in dealing with students' diverse behavior (Casipe & Bete, 2023). Therefore, potential risks such as bullying and child abuse cases in a rural elementary school become evident.

b. Development and Implementation of the Support and Advocacy for a Friendly Environment (SAFE) School Initiative

The Support and Advocacy for a Friendly Environment (SAFE) School Initiative is a school-community-driven initiative that aims to improve and enhance the implementation of the CPP, specifically in a rural elementary school. It comprises of three categories: (a) an orientation workshop that aims to revisit the CPP, enhance the awareness of its components, and the execution of the CPP in school (b) establishment of a Child Protection Committee to strengthen its implementation and (c) provision of a school handbook as a reference of the SAFE School Initiative. Moreover, this aimed to capacitate teachers in exercising their roles and responsibilities as classroom managers and to foster awareness of the school and community as the policy implementers, specifically the parents and the school children.

This initiative is designed to respond to the gathered deficiency of the school's CPP implementation. It is developed and organized based on the recommendations of the school's stakeholders. "*Unang-una, magkaigwa kita sadi na training o orientation about sa CPP para maaraman ta man.*" [First, we need to have a training or orientation on CPP

to enhance our knowledge and understanding], stated by Participant C. *“Magpaseminar talaga o training sa CPP para maging aware kita. Dapat may committee an CPP para sinda an magmanage.”* [We should conduct a seminar or training on CPP to raise awareness and establish a CPC to manage its implementation], expressed by Participant E. *“Dapat may magkapot man san komitiba na maaram mag-agoy, maaram magpakumbaba.”* [There should be a committee composed of individuals with expertise in childcare and with a humble approach], Participant I added. *“Dapat an mga member san CPC oriented sinda san mga roles and responsibilities ninda tapos dapat magkaigwa kita sin guidelines kun nano ba talaga an dapat himuon tapos dapat malinaw sa amon ina na mga policies, kun pan-o disiplinahon ina na pasawayon na batit.”* [The CPC members should be oriented on their roles and responsibilities, and we should have clear guidelines and policies to ensure everyone’s awareness], Participant F denoted. *“Dapat tagan man sin action pagnagsusumat an batit para diri marugda an batit na magsabi sa teacher kun may problema sinda sa laog san eskwelahan kasi pag minsan parang an batit nangbully dahil sa may problema din sinda sa balay, dapat inkakaistorya kuta kun nano an problema san nangbully nan ang inbully para po magkaintindihan, para mas malinaw.”* [When a child reports an incident, prompt action should be taken to encourage them to speak up about problems at school because sometimes a child might be bullying because of the underlying issues at home, so it is crucial to talk to both the bully and the victim to foster better understanding and resolution], Participant J explained.

Relatively, according to Asio et al. (2020), a seminar that aims to revisit the Child Protection Policy is recommended for the awareness of school stakeholders. This recommendation is supported by the study of Bayuca (2020) and Casipe & Bete (2023), which denoted that seminars and training for the school stakeholders are significant in improving or enhancing the CPP implementation. Likewise, capacity building, community engagement, training and program implementation are crucial towards effective implementation of the policy (Andaya et al., 2025; Andaya & Patricio, 2025; Manacho, 2024; Atilano-Tang, 2023). Additionally, according to Estremera (2018), action plans are necessary to enhance awareness and execution of CPP specifically in elementary schools. These recommendations gathered from the interviews and literature are comparable; thus, this initiative contributes a significant improvement to the school’s CPP implementation, and one of these is the establishment of CPC in the school that will spearhead the implementation of the CPP.

A One-Day School-Based Orientation-Workshop on the Implementation of the CPP was approved by the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and granted a budgetary allocation of 6,000 pesos from the school Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) for the food, tarpaulin, and other related expenses through a proposal and an Authority-To-Conduct (ATC). Additionally, SDS permitted the Division Child Protection Coordinator (DCPC) to be the Resource Speaker of the orientation. This activity aimed to capacitate the school stakeholders on the implementation of CPP, foster awareness of its implementation, actively participate in the development and enhancement of CPP implementation, and develop and organize an intervention on the CPP implementation of the school. One of the highlights during the activity was the discussion about DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012 titled “DepEd Child Protection Policy,” and

it was integrated with other legal bases such as RA 7610 and the 1987 Constitution. According to the DCPC, there are misconceptions on the implementation of CPP because some would say that CPP invalidates the rights of the teachers and the parents. He explained that it is not the intention of the policy; thus, awareness of the stakeholders of the CPP implementation is a must to understand their roles and responsibilities. Discipline is not prohibited in CPP, and the rights of the teachers are also protected by the law, he added. Additionally, he stressed that protection is a right, but you must know your obligations as a child or as a teacher. *“Kun halimbawa palampasuhon kamo, [For example, you were asked to sweep the floor,] is it child abuse? No, that is not child abuse. That is part of your training,”* he explained. Consequently, he defined the CPP as *“Yong CPP [the CPP] the purpose is not to expose the child to any activity that is detrimental to their natural development.”* Example *sa loob ng bahay, nagsisigarilyo ka tapos may mga anak ka, [For example, if you smoke indoors while having a child at home], that can be considered as a detrimental activity against your child because science proved it na ang usok ng sigarilyo ay nakakasira ng laman [that cigarette smoke is harmful to the body].*

Relatively, the DCPC stressed the proper administration of the CPP. He shared an example that there was a teacher who caught his/her learner cheating during an exam, but because of the CPP, the teacher just ignored that situation. According to him, the teacher must have an obligation to discipline the child because part of the child protection is discipline, and it cannot be promoted if there's an absence of discipline. Afterwards, he continuously discussed the policy, its definition of terms, the establishment of the CPC with its functions, procedures and referrals in handling bullying and child abuse cases. Another part of the activity was the workshop, where the participants were given a segment of asking questions about their concerns and providing their recommendations for the improvement of the implementation of CPP in the school. Moreover, during this activity, the organization and presentation of the school CPC were established, and each member of the committee signified their support and commitment to being a SAFE School Advocate.

c. Acceptability of the SAFE School Initiative

The acceptability of the school stakeholders to the SAFE School Initiative is paramount to fully implementing the initiative. This part explained the evaluation results on the acceptability of the initiative, which was presented in two themes: strengthened stakeholder awareness of CPP and stakeholder commitment demonstrated through the SAFE School Initiative.

Strengthened Stakeholder Awareness of CPP through the SAFE School Initiative

Awareness of the CPP implementation is the main goal of the initiative; thus, participants expressed their acknowledgement as proof of their acceptability to the initiative. According to Participant E, *“Very helpful siya saamon, especially kami na dai pa knowledgeable sa CPP. Grabe an tabang niya sa amon sa awareness about sa CPP. Grabe an na-gain namon na knowledge about sa CPP. The best interest of the child talaga an pirmo unahon. Iwasan ang pagpalo kay talagang against siya sa CPP.*

Kailangan talaga ang positive discipline sa mga bata kaya mas pabor na ako sa positive discipline.” [This really helps us become more aware of the CPP that we should prioritize the child’s best interest and avoid physical punishment because it’s contrary to CPP principles; hence, positive discipline is essential for children.] “*Since na-orient na kita, makaka-craft na kita sin policy kun pano naton mapoproteksyonan an mga batit, magiging mas safe an eskwelahan at the same time may awareness na din diri lang an mga teachers pati an mga parents.* [With this orientation, we are now equipped to develop a policy to protect children, making our school a safer place. This initiative will also promote awareness among both teachers and parents.] *Kumbaga saro man sinda sa body, may representative sinda sa committee na sainda mismo makakasolicit ka sainda sin mga sitwasyon na pwedeng gibuan sin policy na maaadopt san school para sa mas safe na environment san school, mas magiging mapayapa, mas magiging friendly an school.* [Having them as part of the committee allows us to solicit insights from to inform policy development to create a safer, more peaceful, and child-friendly school.] *Dako-dako na bagay lalo sa aton kasi maiiwasan na, kumbaga aram ta na kun nano an gigibuon ta kumbaga may sistema na, magiging systematic na siya at the same time, kumbaga oriented na kita kun nano an magiging output, maiiwasan na ito halimbawa kun nakagibo man kita sin mga against didto sa protection policy para sa mga batit, maitatama ta na an mga mali naton na practices dati. Kumbaga mafocus na kita kun nano talaga an pinaka-essence san protection policy.*” [This is beneficial because it enables us to be proactive and aware of our actions. With a systematic approach and clear understanding of the expected outcomes, we can avoid violating CPP principles and better understand its purpose], as narrated by Participant D. “*Para saakon kagayon dahil nagkaigwa ako sin experience o kaaraman sa sadiri ko, dagdag na kaaraman dahil ngani sa obligasyon ko, nadagdagan pa an kaaraman ko dahil sadto na orientation naton. Dako-dako na bagay lalo na kun igwa na kita sin magkakapot sadto, makasuporta na. Diri na kita mahirapan kay aram ta na kun nano an gigibuon naton.*” [For me, I found the orientation beneficial as I gained experience and knowledge, especially about my obligations. It’s a big help, especially to have a designated person to oversee and support us. With this guidance, we will be more confident and efficient in our roles], expressed Participant I. “*Magayon siya, ngayon talaga na maka-atendir sadto. Tama talaga na magkaigwa kita sin mga pa-orient or pa-meeting about didto. Mas ngayon talaga na igwa kita committee para mas madisiplina an mga kabatitan*” [It’s beneficial to attend and have an orientation. Having a committee in place will help us discipline children more effectively], Participant J denoted. “*Naliwanagan na ako kay syempre child protection policy an focus niya talagang sa batit so kaipuhan naton sinda proteksyonan pag didi sa laog san school. Pag didi talaga sa school kita an maproteksyon sainda kay wara man iba na maproteksyon sainda kundi kita.* [The CPP orientation has enlightened me on our role in safeguarding children within the school premises since we are the ones responsible for their protection and well-being]. *Magayon na magkaigwa kita irog sana para masolusyonan ina na diri kita aware san mga bagay-bagay para maging aware kita. Syempre makacontribute ito na mga committee, saro pa sinda sa makatabang para mas maging safe an school tapos ina na mga nagbully, mabawasan an mga kasamukan, nan an problema.*” [It’s good that we have this to address issues we’re not aware of. The committee members will contribute and help make the school a safer place, reducing bullying and misbehavior], Participant C added. These statements testify that the SAFE School Initiative has

significantly contributed to awareness of the CPP among the school stakeholders in terms of the use of positive and non-violent discipline, the school-based referral system, and the importance of the establishment of the CPC. Therefore, sustainability of the CPP in the school is feasible through this initiative.

Stakeholder Commitment Demonstrated through the SAFE School Initiative

The partnership of the school and the community is imperative to the implementation of the CPP. Likewise, this initiative requires strong commitment and support from the stakeholders. Because of the initiative, the participants of this study signify their support and commitment through a pledge. According to Participant A, *“As a SAFE School advocate, I commit to become observant in upholding the policy.”* *“Perform my duties and responsibilities as a member of CPC,”* stated Participant B. *“Do my task or duty for the better future of the children,”* Participant C denoted. *“To participate in imposing the CPP and to ensure the best interest of the learner,”* expressed by Participant D. *“Always observe the best interest of the child,”* shared by Participant E. *“Support the CPC to uphold the torch of truth and righteousness,”* according to Participant F. *“A child-friendly environment, creating a child-protected school, always after the welfare of the learners,”* Participant G testified. *“Plan and suggest my ideas in advocating the importance of CPP,”* stated Participant H. *“To participate in the activity, especially in child protection,”* as exclaimed by Participant I. *“Always observe the rights of the children,”* added Participant J. Consequently, the awareness of the CPP had a significant contribution to the stakeholders as an implementer of the CPP. Hence, it is an indication that the school, with its partnership with the community, is ready and eager to perform their roles and responsibilities in securing the welfare of the school children as a SAFE School advocate.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions and recommendations from the needs assessment, implementation, and evaluation of the CPP at the rural elementary school are presented: (a) the school stakeholders need further awareness of the framework, components, and implementation of the CPP; (b) the school has no functional CPC, no reports and records of all proceedings related to bullying and child abuse cases, no written school-based CPP, written procedures to guide in conducting disciplinary proceedings in cases of offenses, inadequate support and training regarding the CPP, and absence of guidelines in community linkages or school-based referral networking for bullying or child abuse cases, (c) teachers have trouble in imposing discipline on their pupils because of invalidating the CPP resulting in accusations, (d) the initiative contributes a significant improvement to the school’s CPP implementation, (e) school stakeholders are ready and eager to perform their roles and responsibilities in securing the welfare of the children. To address these issues, the researchers developed, implemented, and evaluated the SAFE School Initiative, a school-community-driven intervention aimed at enhancing awareness and responsiveness to the CPP, and thus, (f) the initiative has significantly contributed to the enhancement and improvement of the school stakeholders’ awareness and responsiveness of the CPP implementation.

Hence, it is recommended that (a) school heads may adapt the SAFE School Initiative for a comprehensive awareness of CPP of stakeholders, (b) the school may establish a fully functional Child Protection Committee to ensure effective implementation of the CPP, (c) teachers should receive a thorough orientation and training on the use of positive and non-violent discipline for children, (d) the school may sustain and enhance the SAFE School Initiative to realize the full potential of the CPP, (e) the school and the community may cultivate a strong and collaborative commitment to support to strengthened implementation of the CPP, and (f) other researchers may utilize a larger sample, considering its areas of limitations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and concerns were addressed before the interviews were conducted. The participants' collective knowledge and experiences did not disclose their inconsistency and incompetence in the CPP implementation, instead of providing an opportunity to contribute to its development. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by using pseudonyms in the presentation of the results. Their willingness to participate in the study was highly respected, and they were informed that they could withdraw at any time if they felt uncomfortable with the study. Cited authors and researchers were acknowledged in the references section.

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